

MEDICATION ADHERENCE AND QUALITY OF LIFE OF DIABETIC PATIENTS IN RURAL AND URBAN HEALTHCARE FACILITIES IN EDO STATE.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Diabetes mellitus (DM) is on the increase in Nigeria, poor medication adherence has a negative impact on the patient's quality of life (QoL).

Objective: The study aimed to evaluate MA and QoL of DM patients in rural and urban healthcare facilities in Edo State.

Methods: In a descriptive cross-sectional study, data on MA and QoL of DM patients were collected using Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-8), SF-36 QoL. Analysis was both descriptive and inferential. Logistic regression was done to determine association of patient variables to MA. Results were considered significant at $P < 0.05$. Spearman correlation was done to find an association between MA and QoL.

Results: DM patients in rural and urban facilities had low MA -51.8% and 43.2% - respectively. Age and educational qualification were significantly associated with medication adherence in both healthcare facilities with $P < 0.05$ ($r = 0.735$ and 0.569). Gender, duration of DM, and health insurance status were highly significant ($r = 5.136, 2.412$ and -3.563) predictors of MA in Specialist Hospital (SH) Benin. There was low QoL amongst DM participants with Physical Component Summary Score (PCS) of 38.2% and 41.7% and Mental Component Summary Score MCS of 30.2 and 39.2%, respectively. There was a positive correlation (p -value < 0.05) between MA and QoL across all domains in General Hospital (GH) Abudu.

Conclusion: There was suboptimal MA and a below performance QoL among DM patients in rural when compared to an urban healthcare facility.

Keywords: Diabetes mellitus, prevalence, medication adherence, quality of life.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes Mellitus (DM) is a metabolic condition due to the inability of the pancreas to produce adequate insulin or the ineffective utilization of insulin resulting in an increased blood glucose concentration. This often leads to organ damage, paving the way for various complications. There is an increasing prevalence of DM worldwide ^[1], and it constitutes a significant health care system and economic burden for the patients.

It had a worldwide prevalence of 463 million in 2019 and is projected to be 578 and 700m by 2030 and 2045, an Africa prevalence of 4.5% world DM in 2019, which is expected to rise to 5.1% and 5.2% by 2030 2045 ^[1]. A recent meta-analysis reported a 5.8% prevalence in Nigeria ^[2]. Available reports in Nigeria showed crude prevalence rates of 2.2% and 6.8% in 1997 and 2003, respectively ^[3, 4]. Adherence means "the extent to which a person's medication-taking behaviour and lifestyle changes agree with a proposition from a health care provider" ^[5]. Patients can better manage their illnesses by adhering to their medication regimens. Most patients, especially with a chronic illness, experience difficulties in following treatment recommendations. A previous study showed that the medication discontinuation rates on the 30 days of treatment reached 42%, and non-oral treatment of DM had a high risk of discontinuation ^[6].

Medication adherence (MA) is defined as the extent to which patients take medications as prescribed ^[7]. A 50% adherence to long-term therapy for chronic illness has been reported in developed nations and is lower in developing nations ^[8]. The patients do not receive optimal benefits from drug therapy as a result of poor MA. Substandard treatment can lead to an increased burden on available health care services, reduction in patients' QoL and high cost of care ^[9-11].

Poor glycaemic control resulting from non-adherence to medication can increase the risk of DM, related complications, hospital visits, hospitalization and death. Also, QoL, side effects, complex medications and health care system concerns, "demographic, behavioural, treatment, and clinical variables" are among other factors that affect MA ^[12]. Therefore, an

individualized and less complex medication regimen is assumed to be achieved and maintained good glycaemic control.

Quality of life (QoL) is a concept that relates satisfaction and well-being in the physical, psychological, cultural and socio-economic spheres. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines QoL "as individuals' perception of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards and concerns. It is a broad concept affected in a complex way by the person's physical health, psychological state, level of independence, social relationships, personal beliefs and their relationship to salient features of their environment"^[13].

In the treatment of type-2 DM, lifestyle and behavioural modifications are required and may significantly improve the functioning and well-being of patients. Due to the chronic nature and morbidity of DM, QoL patient and their family can be affected. There is a link between the severity of disease and lower QoL^[14]. Successes of long-term maintenance therapy and metabolic control in DM patients depend on their MA and lifestyle changes.

Previous studies in Nigeria have reported MA in tertiary and secondary health care facilities^[15-18]. However, there are few studies comparing MA and QoL of diabetic patients in rural and urban health care facilities. This study, therefore, aimed to evaluate medication adherence and quality of life of diabetic patients, factors associated with MA and correlation between MA and QoL of diabetic patients in both rural and urban health care facilities.

METHODS

Study Design and Setting

This was a cross-sectional study carried out from May 2019 through August 2019 at the Consultant Out-Patients Department (COPD) in Specialist Hospital (SH), Benin City and Out-Patient Unit of General Hospital (GH) Abudu. SH Benin offers comprehensive patient care services for the majority of Edo State indigenes and other neighbouring States. The facility has over 500 beds with different wards and specialities. GH Abudu is a secondary healthcare facility that offers healthcare services to the people of the community and other nearby villages and the neighbouring communities in Delta State. It has about 50 bed spaces for inpatients and runs a general out-patient clinic for patients with different ailments.

Population and sampling

Type-2 DM adults diagnosed more than six months ago who presented to the clinic for follow up were invited to participate in the study. In a convenient sampling, 278 DM patients consisting of 159 patients from SH Benin City and 119 patients from GH Abudu were recruited to participate in the study. Eligible patients were identified and recruited while waiting

for consultation with their respective doctors. These selected patients were provided with an explanatory statement and consent form. The inclusion criteria were age >18 years, currently on oral anti-hyperglycemic medication and consent to participate. Patients visiting the health facility for the first time, those having cardiovascular complications, pregnant females, critically ill patients and those on admission, and patients who could not communicate well with the interviewer were excluded from the study.

Outcome Measure

Primary outcome measures were MA and QoL; other specific measures were associated with MA and the relationship between MA and QoL.

Data Collection and Statistical Analysis

Data on socio-demographic (e.g. age, sex, educational qualification, marital status, employment, income and health insurance status) and disease-related information (e.g. duration of diabetes and numbers of medication) were collected using a well-structured questionnaire. Data on MA and QoL were collected using Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-8)^[19, 20] and SF-36 QoL instruments^[21]. MMAS-8 contains eight questions, which are answerable in the form of YES/NO related to adherence. All items except item 5 were reverse coded, no = 0 and yes = 1. The total score of all items was calculated with a sum score ranging from 0 to 8. Adherence was defined as high adherence, medium adherence and low adherence based on MMAS scores of 8, 6-<8 and < 6, respectively (out of a total score of 8 points). This was later presented in dichotomous data and reclassified as adherence (6-8) and non-adherence (<6). The SF-36 was designed to measure general health status from the patient's point of view. The SF-36 includes eight concepts commonly represented in health surveys: physical functioning, role functioning, bodily pain, general health, vitality, social functioning, emotional, and mental health. Data collected were entered into Microsoft excel and, after that, loaded into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 20 and InStatGraph Pad version 3. Analysis was both descriptive and inferential. Chi-squared test, Spearman correlation and logistic regression were performed for the analyses and results were considered significant with $P < 0.05$. Logistic regression was done to determine association of patient variables to MA. Results were considered significant at $P < 0.05$. The QoL of the patient was analyzed into different health domains based on Regular Scoring (RS) 0 to 100 and Norm Base Scores (NBS) mean = 50, with higher scores indicating better health status. After that, values were transformed into a physical and mental component summary score (PCS and MCS) to allow for a more straightforward interpretation and standardization of the results. The correlations analysis was carried out

to determine the relationship between medication adherence and the patients' quality of life.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Benin, with reference number EC/FP/019/12. Furthermore, written informed consent was obtained from all the participants.

RESULTS

Of the 278 eligible DM patients for the study, 258 (148 from SH Benin and 110 from GH Abudu) filled and returned the questionnaire making a response rate of 92.8%. The average age of the respondents were 54.5±1.09 in GH Abudu and 46±0.75 years in SH Benin, respectively. More than half (54.5%) of the patients in a rural health facility (GH Abudu) were age ≥ 60 years compared to 49.3% of age 40-49 years in SH Benin, 60.9% and 58.8 % were both female in GH Abudu and SH Benin. A majority (81.1%) in SH Benin had educational qualifications up to tertiary level, while one-third (32.7%) in GH Abudu were of Primary school level. A majority (93.9% and 65.5%) were married in SH Benin and GH Abudu. A majority (73.6%) of the participants from SH Benin were employed civil servants, while almost half (46.5%) from GH Abudu were self-employed and were majorly farmers. More than half (56.8%) in SH Benin were of higher income of ≥ N 80,000.00, and 44.5% from GH Abudu received ≤ N20,000.00 as monthly income. 40% of patients in GH Abudu were diagnosed with DM more than ten years ago

compared to 40.5% in SH Benin, whose duration of diabetes was 1 – 5 years. 74.4% and 80.8% of DM patients from SH Benin and GH Abudu were prescribed more than two medication therapy. Only 3.6% and 39.9% from GH Abudu and SH Benin were on the health insurance scheme.

The MA among people with diabetes in both facilities is as shown in Table 1 below. As many as 48.2% of DM patients from GH Abudu and 40.5% from SH Benin did not adhere to their medications. Reasons for not adhering to their medications were severity of illness (42.7% and 43.2%), travelling [49.1% (GH Abudu) and 41.2% (SH Benin)], symptoms under control [45.5% (GH Abudu) and 41.2% (SH Benin)], failure to stick to treatment plan [50.9% (GH Abudu) and 57.4% (SH Benin)] among others.

Generally, there was poor MA among DM patients in both health facilities with 51.8% and 43.2% non-adherence in GH Abudu and SH Benin, and this was considered significant as *P* > 0.05. The factors associated with MA among diabetes patients are shown in Table 2. Age and educational qualification were significantly associated with medication adherence in both healthcare facilities with *P* < 0.05 (*r* = 0.735 and 0.569). Gender, duration of DM, and health insurance status were highly significant (*r* = 5.136, 2.412 and -3.563) predictors of medication adherence in Specialist Hospital Benin. Although there was a positive odd ratio in the respondents' marital, employment, and income status in both healthcare facilities, they were not considered significantly linked to MA.

Table 1: Medication adherence among diabetes patients in both facilities

Variables	GH ABUDU n (%)		SH BENIN n (%)		χ ² , df, P-value
	Yes	No	Yes	No	
Forget to take medicine	53 (48.2)	57 (51.8)	60 (40.5)	88 (59.5)	0.254
Did not take medicine yesterday	53 (48.2)	57 (51.8)	60 (40.5)	88 (59.5)	0.254
Stop taking medicine due to the severity of illness	47 (42.7)	63 (57.3)	64 (43.2)	84 (56.8)	1.000
Forget to take medicine when travelling	54 (49.1)	56 (50.9)	61 (41.2)	87 (58.2)	0.254
Took medication yesterday	48 (43.6)	62 (56.4)	51 (34.5)	97 (65.5)	0.155
Stop taking medicine when symptoms are under control	50 (45.5)	60 (45.5)	61 (41.2)	87 (58.8)	0.526
Feel hassled to stick to the treatment plan	56 (50.9)	54 (49.1)	85 (57.4)	63 (42.6)	0.314
Have difficulty remembering to take medicine.	52 (47.3)	58 (52.7)	58(39.2)	90 (60.8)	0.205
Level of adherence					6.93, 2, 0.031*
High	37 (33.6)		42 (28.4)		
Medium	16 (14.5)		42 (28.4)		
Low	57 (51.8)		64 (43.2)		

Where χ² = Chi-Square, df = degrees of freedom at P value < 0.05

Table 2: Factors associated with medication adherence among diabetes patients

Patient characteristics	Odd ratio	GH ABUDU		P-value	Odd ratio	CH BENIN		P-value
		95% CI for Exp B	Lower-Upper			95% CI for Exp B	Lower-Upper	
Age	0.735	1.231 - 3.533		0.006*	-1.881	0.023 – 1.008		0.041*
Gender	0.399	0.623-3.561		0.370	5.136	17.514 – 1647.1		0.0001**
Education	0.569	1.124 - 2.755		0.014*	-3.698	0.002 -0.268		0.002*
Marital status	0.207	0.816 – 1.854		0.322	-7.514	0.000		0.999
Employment	0.116	0.807 – 1.563		0.491	-2.415	0.002 – 3.249		0.188
Income	0.043	0.789 -1.381		0.762	1.077	0.868 – 9.641		0.083
Duration of DM	-0.217	0-539 – 1.204		0.291	2.412	1.037 – 146.72		0.045*
Health Insurance	-0.969	0.030 – 4.746		0.452	-3.563	0.004 – 0.220		0.001*
Medications	-0.284	0.512 – 1.106		0.148	0.002	0.617 – 1.633		0.995

Where*=significant at p-value <0.05 at 95% CI, GH =General Hospital, CH =Central Hospital

The QoL of the respondents in both healthcare facilities was observed to be generally poor across the domains with Norm Base Score (NBS) < 50 except vitality domain in SH Benin. There was a low Physical Component Score (PCS) 41.7 in SH Benin and 38.7 in GH Abudu and Mental Component (MCS) summary score SH Benin (39.5) and GH Abudu (30.2) among the study participants, respectively. Details of the QoL amongst the study populations are in Table 3. There was a positive correlation (p-value < 0.05) between MA and QoL across all domains in GH Abudu. Only RP, BP, SF and RE domains were significantly (p-value < 0.05) associated with medication adherence among diabetes patients in SH Benin (Table 4).

Table 3: Health quality of life assessment of the respondents

Quality of life domains	GH ABUDU		CH BENIN	
	REGULAR SCORING (RS) 0-100	NORM BASE SCORE (NBS)	REGULAR SCORING (RS) 0-100	NORM BASE SCORE (NBS)
Physical functioning (PF)	52.4± 25.9	27.4	57.8±17.1	35.9
Role Physical (RP)	11.5±5.2	22.4	19.4±9.4	24.5
Bodily Pain (BP)	38.4± 15.3	34.5	58.1±24.5	44.9
General Health (GH)	59.6±10.9	46.6	59.6±18.9	47.1
Vitality (VT)	52.7±17.7	43	60.8±20.2	50.6
Social Functioning (SF)	61.7±13.1	41.6	74.8±22.8	46.5
Role Emotional (RE)	23.6±8.2	38.4	19.6±6.7	20.4
Mental Health (MH)	60.8±12.8	46.4	71.7±18.6	47.6
Physical Component Summary Score (PCS)		38.7		41.7
Mental Component Summary Score (MCS)		30.2		39.5

Table 4: Association between medication adherence and quality of life

Quality of life domains	GH ADUDU		CH BENIN	
	Correlation factor	P-value	Correlation factor	P-value
Physical functioning (PF)	1	-	1	-
Role Physical (RP)	0.422	0.0001**	0.467	0.0001**
Bodily Pain (BP)	0.367	0.0001**	0.424	0.0001**
General Health (GH)	0.534	0.0001**	0.096	0.246
Vitality (VT)	0.359	0.0001**	0.03	0.721
Social Functioning (SF)	0.525	0.0001**	0.452	0.0001**
Role Emotional (RE)	0.281	0.003*	0.166	0.04*
Mental Health (MH)	0.247	0.009*	0.068	0.411

DISCUSSION

This study evaluated the MA and QoL among DM patients in rural and urban health care facilities and determined associated factors to MA and QoL among the participants.

The study observed that female patients were more affected by DM. This is similar to a study done by Mohammadi *et al.* [22], which reported that females are more preponderant but opposed to other studies about the Indian population [23-25]. This may be because ours is a female-dominated society and is more concerned about their health status and may report for consultations more than their male partner. In addition, the study revealed that more rural DM patients were diagnosed for over ten years compared to urban patients. This observation contrasted with the findings from other studies, which showed most DM patients with less than five years duration [26] similar to the other study, showing a median duration of diabetes of 6 years [27].

The findings from the study revealed a suboptimal adherence to medications among DM patients in a rural healthcare facility compared to SH Benin. Adherence level in rural healthcare centres is similar to a study in Malaysia [28], which reported an adherence rate of 47%, but much lower to a study conducted in Ibadan, which revealed that 59% of patients on anti-diabetic drugs were non-adherent to their medications due to lack of finance [29]. Similar studies had also recorded much higher findings reported from Iran (74.8%) [30] and Nigeria (72.5%) [31]. These observed differences in the level of adherence among DM patients in the two health facilities could result from factors relating to health care settings and socio-economic status and methods used for assessing adherence. The poor adherence reported in this study may be attributed to a high level of poly-pharmacy due to increased complications associated with patients with diabetes hypertensive comorbidity. In addition, there is usually out pocket payment for medications. As a result, many people cannot afford their medications.

Major reasons for poor MA were forgetfulness, the

severity of illness, travelling, symptoms under control and failure to stick to the treatment plan. Other studies have also revealed side effects and finance as reasons for non-adherence to medications [29, 31]. Age and education were associated with adherence in both facilities, but gender, duration of DM, and health insurance status were highly significant predictors of medication adherence in SH Benin. This result suggests that the higher the duration of illness, the less likely a patient is to adhere to prescribed medications. There was a significant association between medication adherence and gender in SH Benin. This shows that there were more women than men. Other studies found the female gender associated with poor anti-diabetic medication adherence [32, 33]. This could be explained by the fact that women are more prone to stress and develop mental and emotional disorders like depression. These attributed factors were however not assessed in the current study. Previous studies have also found a relationship between complex drug regimens, cost and side effects of medications, advanced age, female gender, long duration of diabetes, and comorbid conditions to medication adherence [33-36]. Evaluation of MA is essential in chronic diseases like Type-2 DM, where regular medication also affects disease outcomes. In our study majority of the patients reported medium to low adherence. Compliance with a prescribed therapy can further be enhanced by securing an excellent doctor-patient relationship and adequate counselling regarding the chronic nature of the disease.

There was a below performance quality of life across major domains except vitality domain for SH Benin in our study with low Physical Component Summary (PCS) and Mental health Component Summary (MCS) scores. The results suggest that diabetes mellitus has a strong influence on the subjects QoL. In a similar study by Young *et al.*, the majority had an overall positive quality of life [37]. The present findings of a low QoL might be related to the association of chronic disease, increased complications, depression [38] and loneliness [39] and decline cognitive function linked with type-2 diabetes in old age [40].

This study observed that adherence to medications was positively correlated with QoL across all the domains. Other previous studies have stated that DM had a negative impact on patients' quality of life and that comorbidity may further decrease patients' quality of life^[41]. This is in accordance with other studies, suggesting that improved QoL in DM patients may influence treatment adherence, satisfactorily enhance clinical outcomes and reduce morbidity and mortality rates and disease progression^[42].

Some studies^[43, 44] revealed an association between QoL levels in DM patients with better treatment adherence; however, other research has not identified this association^[45]. In contrast, a previous study by Martinez^[27] showed no association between medication adherence and QoL.

However, the study is not without limitations; although there were correlations between MA and QoL, the study was a cross-sectional design and could not conclude on the causal relationship between MA and QoL. Further studies using a longitudinal design can help to examine the time-varying relationship between MA and QoL. In addition, the small sample size of patients used in our study may have limited the power of the analysis. Thus, results cannot be generalized. In addition, other factors such as the use of other medications and the frequency of dosage, costs, and side effects of medication that may influence adherence should also be assessed. Finally, there could be subject recall bias as most respondents relied on self-reported data regarding their medications.

CONCLUSION

Poor MA and QoL were observed in a rural healthcare facility in Edo State, Nigeria. Significant determinants of adherence were age, education, gender, duration of illness and health insurance status. In addition, there was an association between QoL and MA among DM patients in both settings. These findings provide evidence for healthcare professionals and policymakers to develop and evaluate strategies to improve medication adherence and health-related quality of life in rural and urban dwellers.

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REFERENCES

1. International diabetes foundation. Diabetes atlas. 2019 Available from: <http://www.idf.org/diabetesatlas> (Accessed October 13, 2019)
2. Uloko AE, Musa BM, Ramalan MA, Gezawa ID, Puepet FH, Uloko AT, MM. Borodo. KB. Sada (2018). Prevalence and risk factors for diabetes mellitus in Nigeria: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Diabetes Therapy*. 9(3):1307–16.
3. Akinkugbe O. Non-communicable diseases in Nigeria: final report of national survey, Federal Ministry of Health and Social Services, Lagos;1997; 25-26
4. Nyenwe, EA, Odia OJ, Ihekwa AE, Ojule A, Babatunde S. Type 2 diabetes in adult Nigerians: a study of its prevalence and risk factors in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract* 2003; 62: 177-185.
5. Cramer J, Roy A, Burrell A, et al. Medication Compliance and Persistence: Terminology and Definitions. *Value in Health*; 2008; 11(1): 44 - 47.
6. Perwitasari D, Urbayatun S. Treatment Adherence and Quality of Life in Diabetes Mellitus Patients in Indonesia. *SAGE Open*. 2016; 6(2): 215824401664374.
7. Osterberg L, Blaschke T. Drug therapy. Adherence to medication. *N Engl J Med* 2005;353:487–497.
8. World Health Organization. Adherence to Long-term Therapies: Evidence for action. Geneva, Switzerland: 2003; WHO.
9. Lau DT, Nau DP. Oral anti-hyperglycemic medication non-adherence and subsequent hospitalization among type 2 diabetes. *Diabetes Care*. 2004; 27: 2149-2153.
10. Sokol MC, McGuigan KA, Verbrugge RR, Epstein RS. Impact of medication adherence on hospitalization risk and healthcare cost. *Medcare*; 2005; 43(6): 521-530.
11. Krousel-Wood M, Joyce C, Holt EW, Levitan EB, Dornelles A, Webber LS, Muntner P. Development and evaluation of a self-report tool to predict low pharmacy refill adherence in elderly patients with uncontrolled hypertension. *Pharmacotherapy*. 2013; 33(8): 798-811
12. Gusmai Lde F, Novato Tde S, Nogueira Lde S. The influence of quality of life in treatment adherence of diabetic patients: a systematic review. *Rev Esc Enferm USP*; 2015; 49(5): 839-46.
13. WHOQOL Group. The WHO quality of life assessment (WHOQOL): Development and general psychometric properties. *Soc Sci Med*; 1998; 46: 1569-83.
14. Huang I, Hwang CC, Wu MY, Lin W, Leite W, Wu AW. Diabetes-specific or generic measures for health-related quality of life? evidence from psychometric validation of the D-39 and SF-36. *Value Health*. 2008; 11(3): 450–61.
15. Adisa R, Fakeye TO, Fasanmade A. Medication adherence among ambulatory patients with type 2 diabetes in a tertiary healthcare setting in southwestern Nigeria. *Pharm Pract*; 2011; 9:72–81.
16. Yusuff KB, Obe O, Joseph BY. Adherence to anti-diabetic drug therapy and self-management practices among type-2 diabetics in Nigeria. *Pharm World Sci* 2008; 30: 876–883.
17. Jackson IL, Adibe MO, Okonta MJ, Ukwe CV. Medication adherence in type 2 diabetes patients in Nigeria. *Diabetes Technol Ther*. 2015; 17(6): 398-404.
18. Ababio GK, Bosomprah S, Olumide A, et al. Predictors of quality of life in patients with diabetes mellitus in two tertiary health institutions in Ghana and Nigeria. *Niger Postgrad Med J*. 2017; 24: 48-55

19. Morisky, D. E., Ang, A., Krousel-Wood, M., & Ward, H. Predictive validity of a medication adherence measure for hypertension control. *Journal of Clinical Hypertension*, 2008; 10(5), 348–354.
20. Krousel-Wood, M. A., Islam, T., Webber, L. S., Re, R. N., Morisky, D. E., & Muntner, P. New medication adherence scale versus pharmacy fill rates in seniors with hypertension. *American Journal of Managed Care*, 2009; 15(1), 59–66.
21. Ware Jr JE, Sherbourne CD. The MOS 36-item short-form health survey (SF-36). I. Conceptual framework and item selection. *Med Care*. 1992;30(6):473–83.
22. Mohammadi S, Karim N, Abd. Talib R and Amani R: Evaluation of quality of life among type 2 diabetes patients. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*. 2016; 51 - 56.
23. Patel M, Patel I, Patel Y, Rath S. A Hospital-based Observational Study of Type 2 Diabetic Subjects from Gujarat, India. *Journal of Health, Population and Nutrition*. 2011; 29(3): 265-72.
24. Churi S, Ravi Kumar Y and Abdi S: Study of drug utilization pattern of anti-hyperglycemic agents in a South Indian tertiary care teaching hospital. *Indian Journal of Pharmacology*. 2012; 44(2): 210-4.
25. Ramesh R, Kumar SV, Gopinath S, Gavaskar B and Gandhiji G. Diabetic knowledge of rural community and drug utilization pattern in a tertiary care hospital. *International Journal of Pharmacy & Life Sciences* 2011; 2(1): 531-5.
26. Upadhyay D K, Palaian S, Shankar PR, Mishra P and Saha K: Prescribing Pattern in diabetic out-patients in a tertiary care teaching hospital in Nepal. *Journal of clinical and diagnostic research* 2007; 3: 248 - 255.
27. Martínez Y, Prado-Aguilar C, Rascón-Pacheco R and Valdivia-Martínez J: Quality of life associated with treatment adherence in patients with type 2 diabetes: a cross-sectional study. *BMC Health Services Research*. 2008; 8(1):164.
28. Ahmad NS, Ramli A, Islahudin F, Paraidathathu T. Medication adherence in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus treated at primary health clinics in Malaysia. *Patient Prefer Adherence* 2013;17(7):525–30.
29. Yusuff Kazeem, Obe , Joseph Bonatson. Adherence to anti-diabetic drug therapy and self-management practices among type-2 diabetics in Nigeria. *Pharm World Sci*. 2008;30(6):876-883.
30. Yekta Z, Pourali R, Aghassi MR, Ashragh N, Ravanyar L, Pour MYR. Assessment of self-care practice and its associated factors among diabetic patients in an urban area of Urmia, northwest Iran. *J Res Health Sci* 2011;11:33–7.
31. Pascal IGU, Ofoedu JN, Uchenna NP, Nkwa AA, Uchamma GUE. Blood glucose control and medication adherence among adult type 2 diabetic Nigerians attending a primary care clinic in an under-resourced environment of eastern Nigeria. *N Am J Med Sci* 2012;4:310–5
32. Sajith M, Pankaj M, Pawar A, Modi A, Sumariya R. Medication adherence to anti-diabetic therapy in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Young*. 2014;18:7.
33. Kalyango JN, Owino E, Nambuya AP. Non-adherence to diabetes treatment at Mulago Hospital in Uganda: prevalence and associated factors. *Afr Health Sci*. 2008;8:67–73.
34. Rubin Richard. Adherence to pharmacologic therapy in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *Am J Med*. 2005; 118(5):27-34.
35. Tiv Michel, Viel J-F, Mauny F. Medication adherence in Type 2 Diabetes: The ENTRED Study 2007, a French Population-Based Study. *PLoS ONE* 2012. ;7(3):e32412.
36. Young Y, Frick KD, Phelan EA. Can successful ageing and chronic illness coexist in the same individual? A multidimensional concept of successful ageing. *J Am Med Dir Assoc*, 2009; 10(2):87–92.
37. Chapman DP, Perry GS, Strine TW. The vital link between chronic disease and depressive disorders. *Prev Chronic Dis*, 2005;2(1): A14.
38. Pinquart M, Sörensen S. Risk factors for loneliness in adulthood and old age—a meta-analysis. In *Advances in psychology research*. Edited by Shohov SP. Hauppauge: Nova Science Publishers; 2003; 111–143.
39. Hassing LB, Grant MD, Hofer SM, et al. Type 2 diabetes mellitus contributes to cognitive decline in old age: a longitudinal-based study. *J Int Neuropsychol Soc*, 2004; 10(4):599–607.
40. Wandell, P. E. Quality of life of patients with diabetes mellitus. An overview of research in primary health care in the Nordic countries. *Scandinavian Journal of Primary Health Care*, 2005; 23, 68-74.
41. Farias MS, Agra CC, Araujo LK, Correia DS, Cavalcante JC. Treatment adherence and life quality of diabetic patients assisted in the primary care division. *Rev Soc Bras Clí n Med*. 2014;12(2):102–7.
42. Hassan K, Loar R, Anderson BJ, Heptulla RA. The role of socio-economic status, depression, quality of life, and glycemic control in type 1 diabetes mellitus. *Journal of Pediatrics*. 2006; 149(4):526–31
43. Puri K, Sapra S, Jain V. Emotional, behavioural and cognitive profile, and quality of life of Indian children and adolescents with type 1 diabetes. *Indian Journal Endocrinology and Metabolism*. 2013; 17(6):1078–83.
44. O'Neil KJ, Jonnalagadda SS, Hopkins BL, Kicklighter JR. Quality of life and diabetes knowledge of young persons with type 1 diabetes: influence of treatment modalities and demographics. *Journal of American Dietetic Association*. 2005; 105(1):85–91.